

QUIZ**LAST NAME: OJABO****FIRST NAME: EDWARD****PROGRAM CODE: MTSD****COURSE CODE: ACA 401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian in-text/parenthetical.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access).

The author used MSWord 2019 on Windows 10.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What are the three main parts of an academic essay?**

- The introduction, the body, and the conclusion.¹**
- The hook, the main idea, and the conclusion.
- The topic sentence, the body, and the conclusion.
- The evidence, the claim, and the conclusion.

2. **The following are considered plagiarism EXCEPT?**

- Copying and pasting passages from electronic sources without placing the passages in quotes and properly citing the source.¹
- Translating from one language to another without properly citing the original source.
- Summarizing ideas without citing their source.

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

- Citing an author or source that has provided the information used by the writer.²**
3. **What are the CORRECT steps in the writing process?**
- Revising, Prewriting, Writing, Editing, and Publishing
 - Writing, Prewriting, Editing, Revising, and Publishing.
 - Prewriting, Writing, Revising, Editing, and Publishing.³**
 - Prewriting, Writing, Editing, Revising, and Publishing.
4. **Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations outlines which two citation styles?**
- Book-Date Style and Title-Bibliography Style.
 - Author-Date Style and Notes-Bibliography Style.⁴**
 - Title-Date Style and Title-Bibliography Style.
 - Author-Time Style and Notes-Citation Style.
5. **What is a Claim?**
- A statement used to support or prove the thesis.⁵**
 - A sentence that grabs your reader's attention.

² Ibid., 5-10.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 9th ed. (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 5-7.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, revised. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87-88.

⁵ Ibid., 37-40.

- The analysis explaining the meaning of evidence.
- Quotations from a source.

6. **All of these are types of questions researcher ask, EXCEPT?**

- Conceptual Questions.
- Practical Questions.
- Applied Questions.
- Analytical Questions.**⁶

7. **A writer does not need to provide a citation, EXCEPT?**

- When the writer expresses his ideas, theories, arguments, conclusions.
- Where surveys and experiments are designed and carried out by the writer.
- When the writer uses ideas from, refer to, or quote from, another person's work.**⁷
- When conveying fundamental common knowledge.

8. **Citations are inserted in the WHO text using either the System or a numerical system.**

- The Harvard System.**⁸

⁶ Ibid., 16-17.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 55-58.

⁸ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004), 24.

- The American Psychological Association (APA) System.
 - The Chicago System.
 - The American Medical Association (AMA) System.
9. **The spelling of disease names and other medical terms follows usage?**
- French.
 - Russian.
 - British.**⁹
 - American.
10. **The European Commission Publications Office positions footnote references in before punctuation for uniformity across language versions.**
- Inverted Comma.
 - Quotes.
 - Brackets.**¹⁰
 - Semi-colon.

⁹ Ibid., 30.

¹⁰ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. *English Style Guide A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2011), 41.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. 2011. *English Style Guide A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. European Commission.

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. 9th ed. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.